

Alternative Assessment in the EFL Environment: A Project-Based Approach

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Abstract: This article focuses on examining how alternative assessment can become a very successful teaching tool in the hands of educators who wish to assess their students' performance in a non-traditional way. In order to achieve such an aim, the teacher chose to create three projects, which were based on the coursebook material, and focus on classroom observation methodology by incorporating a student observation checklist and three different types of assessment forms per project: a student self-assessment form as well as group-to-group and within-group peer assessment ones. The choice of such material is based on the benefits of project-based learning. As well as that, self-assessment forms and peer/group assessment enhance student autonomy, boost collaboration within the classroom and offer an enjoyable and meaningful alternative to more traditional and rigid forms of student evaluation such as standardised testing. The three projects were concluded in corresponding teaching sessions which aimed at different skills, after which sessions there followed an evaluation process implementing everything mentioned above.

Keywords: alternative assessment, project-based learning, checklist, collaboration, critical thinking.

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1. Introduction

Traditionally, in the field of TENOR (Teaching English for No Obvious Reason), the easiest and most convenient way for teachers to assess language performance has been via the implementation of standardised tests. Such tests are carried out usually because of curriculum and school administration demands and also either to *assist* or *assess* learning; the former entails developmental/formative assessment which aims at evaluating how effective learning has been by providing constructive feedback to teachers as well as students so as to make amends for the future whereas the latter is connected with examinations that provide learners with language certificates which ascertain aptitude (West, 2004, in Kofou et al., 2019). However, this system has proven somewhat deficient in measuring student performance in terms of specified learning goals and overall quality of language taught (Monib et al., 2020) so alternative forms of assessment have emerged which focus on language use in an authentic environment in which students have to apply critical thinking while working on varied tasks and activities (Al Ruqeishi, 2015, in Monib et al., 2020). To that end, a set of original tasksheets was created for the teacher to become involved in alternative assessment and analyse its role and implications in enhancing student language performance.

2. Why Alternative Assessment

Growing discontent regarding standardised test utility as a primary source of information pertinent to learner aptitude (Tsagari, 2004, in Kofou et al., 2019) has urged educators to move toward more holistic ways of assessing performance. As Barootchi and Keshavarz (2002, in Kofou et al., 2019) maintain, on one hand, traditional testing fails to provide teachers with detailed information on the *how* and *what* of learning and, on the other hand, it may prove insufficient in measuring student improvement in time, which is important for teachers in order to draw assumptions as to the right path and methodology to follow. Additionally, tests fail to assess the ability of students to resort to different learning strategies in their effort to acquire language (McNamara, 2000, in Mendoza, 2009, in Putri et al., 2019). Apart from that, alternative assessment methods can become an interesting and entertaining way of keeping students motivated all the while promoting equality (Yildirim, 2013, in Putri et al., 2019) as all parties may air their views in open discussion. Last, on a psychological level, learners feel actively involved in the learning process, they can openly express their needs and wants and, as a result, they may feel more motivated and self-confident (Tsagari, 2004, in Kofou et al., 2019). As for teachers, alternative assessment is efficient in boosting professional growth as it can eliminate shameful feelings of contingent incompetence which may also cause stress (Shepard, 1991, in Tsagari, 2004, in Kofou et al., 2019).

3. Teaching Context

The class in question consists of four individuals (two male twins aged 10 and two female aged 9 and 11) who attend elementary school. They are part of an English foreign language school and their language level is A2 CEFR (2020). Students at this level should be able to comprehend everyday language linked to their immediate environment as well as likes and preferences, they should be able to carry out straightforward and explicit tasks pertinent to their interests and finally they should be able to engage in oral and written communication so as to express basic information connected to family life, school environment, hobbies and leisure time activities (Sifakis, 2004). The teacher is bilingual (Greek-Italian), holds a degree in Teaching English as a Foreign Language from the Kapodistrian University of Athens and has a 19-year-teaching experience to students of all levels (preA1-C2) and different age range. The class is homogenous as all individuals share a common native language (Greek) and come from similar social as well as financial backgrounds. The coursebook used for this class is “*Hashtag English 2*” by Express Publishing and school facilities accommodate multimodality with the aid of IWB (interactive whiteboard) material so as to boost 21st century skills and computer literacy (Elola & Oskoz, 2017). The teacher chose to implement class observation as a means of alternative assessment via the procedure of PBL (project-based learning). The procedure was carried out during several sessions that pertain to three of the six corresponding modules included in the textbook and served as a complement to the revision tests taken at the end of every module (see appx).

4. Methodology

4.1 Material Description

The teacher focused on three projects (see appx) included in the coursebook so as to devise and implement classroom observation with the aid of a student observation checklist, a student self-assessment form as well as group-to-group and within-group peer assessment forms (see appx). Each project was to be conducted in three 50-minute sessions and concentrated on different skills, vocabulary and grammar so as to help students revise the module material and present the tutor with a clearer picture as to whether lesson aim and objectives were met.

The topic of Project 1 is “*sports*” and, apart from inventing a sport, the aim of the lesson is to help learners develop creative skills. The teacher chose to focus on building speaking strategies so that learners could practice sport-related vocabulary and the use of the Present Simple tense. Among other things, lesson objectives include *21st century skills* that entail problem-solving, collaboration, communication, autonomy and self-awareness (Chu et al., 2017). Apart from that, the lessons enhance computer literacy, an important characteristic of the *i-Generation* (digital natives of the 90s-2000s) (Carlson, 2005, in Avgerou, Vlachos, 2016); as well as that, they incorporate the element of Language Across the Curriculum, which offers a variety of possibilities for language use in a varied context-be it in other subjects, activities and so on (Halliwell, 1997, in Anastasiadou, Alexiou, 2020). The final product is for the class to create a powerpoint presentation and present their work orally.

The second Project, “*flying cars*”, aims at helping students identify problems in the manufacturing of future cars with the ultimate aim of boosting problem-solving techniques. Grammar and lexis

include the use of Past Simple and transport verbs. The project integrates reading and writing so as to urge students to resort to skimming and scanning for information, which information should then be used to create an entry for the school blog. The students are thus involved in *collaborative writing* which may result in improvement in writing performance since students are compelled to interact so as to create joint content (Khatib, 2014). As well as that, individuals of different abilities and aptitude work together and exchange pieces of information which are then joined under new meaning (Ohta, 2000, Storch, 2002, in Khatib, 2014); this process helps the less able individuals become more confident and perform better (Khatib, 2014).

The last project, “*Healthy pets!*”, aims at developing ICT research skills. Students are invited to use topic-related vocabulary and relevant grammatical structures (modals, quantifiers) so as to talk about pets and give advice on healthy pet habits. The project focuses on boosting oral performance, a skill which the revision test cannot assess since it only incorporates reading, writing, listening, apart from grammatical and lexical items. The end product is a poster which students are invited to create while working together and then they should present it orally.

It is worth noting that all three projects include the element of culture so as to ultimately build intercultural competence among learners, which is an important aspect of the modern classroom (Kiose et al., 2019, in Anastasiadou, Alexiou, 2020).

As mentioned above, in order to evaluate classroom activity, the teacher created observation checklists and self- as well as peer assessment forms, which will be thoroughly explained in the following sections.

4.2 Classroom Observation and Project-Based Learning

As Bailey (2001, in Tsagari, 2004, in Kofou et al., 2019) explains, classroom observation entails the careful monitoring of student/teacher work, which information is, in turn, gathered and analysed systematically so as for the parties involved to draw meaningful conclusions on the success of the learning process. Moreover, it can prove useful in making assumptions on the washforward effect of teaching in the sense that learners are monitored regarding acquired knowledge, abilities and comprehension, and that information is then examined by the tutor who openly engages in group conversation with students in order to ultimately make the necessary adjustments and enhance learning conditions (Tsagari, 2004, in Kofou et al., 2019). Assessment through observation may become a great opportunity for mutual growth as both parties study, record and master classroom techniques which can become useful in the real world outside the classroom (Devos, 2014). However, since learning is a dynamic process that joins together distinct individuals who create a unique environment where situations may unfold unpredictably (Richards & Farrell, 2005, in Devos, 2014), it may be difficult for class observation to take place without any problems; after all, handling many pieces of information simultaneously in a complex context may be a difficult task for educators who view this as an opportunity for professional development as well (Devos, 2014). Despite the difficulties, it can be claimed that assessment via observation is overall a fruitful and mostly enjoyable experience for all those involved.

Regarding project-based learning and its benefits to students, especially younger ones, as Brewster et al. (1992, in Zouganeli,

2004, in Anastasiadou, Alexiou, 2020) explain, when learners become involved in the transfer of pre-acquired skills and knowledge to other learning instances, then they build strategies that pertain to critical thinking, problem-solving and choice-making which can prove useful in other subjects and courses too. What is more, when students engage in topic-based activities, they develop their creativity, not to mention the fact that they approach tasks in a somewhat scientific as well as inquisitive manner (Zouganeli, 2004, in Anastasiadou, Alexiou, 2020). As well as that, such theme-based projects support the *how* and *why* of learning, which means specific learning circumstances, notions and ideas shared as well as a reason for participating (Halliwell, 1992, Vale & Feunteun, 1995, in Zouganeli, 2004, in Anastasiadou, Alexiou, 2020).

In terms of project-based assessment, when learners become active participants in situations that simulate reality, then they may become more knowledgeable as they will probably have mastered life skills (Griva & Kofou, 2017) such as communication, collaboration, investigation, self-evaluation, observation and problem-solving techniques (Simonson et al., 2000, in Nasab, 2015, in Griva, Kofou, 2017).

4.3 Observation Checklists

When opting for classroom observation, one challenge the teacher is often faced with is whether the material can be organised and recorded systematically and effectively for further reference (Tsagari, 2004, in Kofou et al., 2019). Before devising the checklists the first step was to identify the areas of interest which would enable the tutor to understand if what was taught was eventually learnt (washback effect) in order to consequently move forward with teaching; also, based on Genesee and Upshur (1996, in Kofou et al., 2019) it was essential that, upon process completion, gathered information should enable the teacher to also identify any difficulties that arose during the process so as to carefully plan the next step of instruction.

As concerns the areas of focus, it was decided to assess both *linguistic* as well as *non-linguistic* aspects, as explained by Genesee and Upshur (ibid). In relation to the former, the teacher included elements of student performance on the various skills (speaking, writing, reading); as well as that, she decided to focus on vocabulary and grammar knowledge, besides other items pertinent to communicative ability, for instance. The non-linguistic items included in the checklist are relevant to the different strategies the learners might employ, working modes (for example, preference to group or individual work), behavioural patterns and reaction to any type of difficulty they might encounter.

Projects require that learners work in groups but they may also entail individual work, so it was concluded that both self-assessment checklists be created for students to engage in self-evaluation, as well as group-to-group and within-group checklists. Assessing individual work provides all parties with detailed information on learners' strengths and weaknesses and plan future action for improvement purposes, which information can also be introduced to parents, school administration etc for informative reasons. Evaluating groups of learners may present a more general picture of student tactics, however, it is less time-consuming, it includes all the class in the process and is essential in understanding whether individuals collaborate successfully (ibid).

Concerning the right time to assess, it was decided to follow the

steps of project-based learning and hand out the evaluation forms after the creation of the end-product so as to consider both the *process* and the *product*, as explained by Phillips et al. (1999, in Zouganeli, 2004, in Anastasiadou, Alexiou, 2020): this means the teacher and students collaborating and pondering over what was learnt and the reasons why, with the aim of evaluating their success. It is through this process that materials and approach can eventually be re-adapted to suit the needs of learners; as well as that, students become aware of their own capabilities and thus become more self-aware and self-reliant (ibid).

Finally, as advised by Genesee and Upshur (1996, in Kofou et al., 2019) the checklists would be kept as record for future reference so that the teacher would infer on learner overall aptitude and performance in time; she would also understand whether she may intervene and on which instances during the course so as to make all the necessary adjustments that may boost knowledge. Lastly, parents and administration would have access to information at any time and they would monitor student success, which would be complementary to assigning grades.

4.4 Peer and Self-Assessment

The decision to include a self-assessment form was based on the idea that the information provided would link teacher feedback with individual students' learning modes (Orsmond et al., 2000, in Peng, 2010) in the sense that learners would reflect upon their work in order to identify strengths and weaknesses and then engage in meaningful conversation with their tutor. Thus, it can be claimed that this process can boost critical thinking as well as enhance metacognition (Lin et al., 2001, Topping, 1998, in Griva, Kofou, 2017). In addition, by being directly involved in learning, students become more motivated, responsible and self-aware (Sivan, 2000, in Peng, 2010). Also, the more feedback they receive, the more they build high-order thinking skills (Topping, 1998, in Peng, 2010) and feel more independent (Orsmond, Merry, 1996, Sivan, 2000, in Peng, 2010). Furthermore, self-assessment within a project enables learners to identify how far they contribute to learning individually, as opposed to when being part of a group (Li, 2001, in Peng, 2010) since students create their own path to knowledge (Brown, 2004, in Peng, 2010). Finally, individuals are trained to identify their own errors, which is an essential life skill, they become more determined and learn to set and accomplish their goals (Kavlu, 2015).

As regards peer assessment, there are several benefits of incorporating it in projects. One major advantage is that, apart from their own work, learners are asked to evaluate the work of their fellow students in terms of quality and performance, which leads to better recognising and elaborating upon evaluation standards (Patri, 2002, in Peng, 2010). As well as that, it helps deconstruct the notion that the teacher is the only one burdened with making the correct inferences pertinent to student evaluation (Orsmond, Merry, 1996, in Peng, 2010). One last point in favour of peer assessment is that students are actively involved in assessing their peers' end product, which happens through active participation in social exchanges within an expressive environment that simulates reality; as a result, learners gain knowledge in a holistic way, not to mention the fact that assessment becomes a less stressful experience (Kavlu, 2015).

The idea of creating within-group and group-to-group assessment checklists was based on the fact that, on one hand, group members would engage in evaluating their own participation in group

activity and, on the other hand, every group would assess the other party's contribution to the end product (Peng, 2010). Within group evaluation can be more convenient in aiding learners to realise their fellow students' opinions of their effort; this takes place via open discussion during which individuals are urged to air their views and comment on the validity of the process in terms of the washforward effect it may have on learning, not to mention the fact that it may eliminate idleness and inertia on the part of the less hard-working learners who may depend on others to complete the task (ibid). Group-to-group assessment enables the evaluation of the contribution each group makes to the task. Thus, students are encouraged to assess the other group and identify their possible strong as well as weak points (Kavlu, 2015). It should be mentioned, however, that this is something which might not be possible to occur smoothly as it may be challenging for learners to evaluate friendly peers and, of course, there may be different understandings of aptitude which, in turn, may hinder correct assessment (Peng, 2010).

It is worth noting that, before initiating peer and self-assessment, the teacher should bear in mind some suggestions made by Falchikov (2005, in Peng, 2010) so as to enhance the process: assuming that students have prior experience in the method (for instance, the advantages as well as the aim and criteria of the procedure have been made clear during a previous session), in order for assessment to take place, it is essential to hand out the forms, allow time for completion and then involve all individuals in open discussion so as to boost students' self-esteem and reduce stress. Of course, it is important to guarantee anonymity as this may lower the impact friendly bonds can have on evaluating peers; this could be safeguarded if within-group evaluation forms are sent through confidential electronic mail. Lastly, classroom discussion prior to assessment enables objectivity and makes students more accepting of criticism.

5. Implications

According to Devenney (1989, in Peng, 2010), alternative assessment serves a different purpose for teachers as opposed to students: teachers resort to it due to summative evaluation, in the sense that they can infer on learning results for future reference; for students, it is part of their formative assessment as an aspect of the continuing learning procedure. This modern way of assessing students does not substitute for conventional means of evaluation such as tests; it can be claimed that it can work in a complementary way by enhancing learning as individuals actively participate and feel empowered (Topping, 1998, in Peng, 2010). Therefore, it can be said that high levels of validity and reliability are not the central aim of alternative assessment; on the contrary, it is more important to grasp the logic behind such a practice and that way involve teachers as well as students in controlling materials, the process and the results (Cheng, Warren, 2005, in Peng, 2010). After all, in this case, validity can be guaranteed when the link between tutor and learner assumptions that are pertinent to grading are investigated and the results are identified, which leads to enhancing and adjusting material so as to create better future learning conditions (Falchikov, 2005, in Peng, 2010). Lest we forget, formative assessment is an ongoing process of evaluating students and drawing inference on how learners work to construct knowledge, how they build learning techniques through experience, how well they cooperate as well as how capable they are of resolving issues (Griva, Kofou, 2017).

Apart from the above, Singh et al. (2022) cite various benefits of alternative assessment for students: first and foremost, it promotes high-order thinking strategies as learners exhibit varied abilities in different skills, they build elaboration strategies and air their opinions in a safe environment. As for teachers, they create and cherish strong bonds with their students. Additionally, learners become aware of their abilities and challenges through authentic tasks that emulate reality. This results in holistic learning as different features of language are assembled and cross-examined (Hamayan, 1995) in an integrated manner which aims at encompassing the individual's various talents and expertise (Tierney et al., 1991, in Hamayan, 1995). Finally, alternative assessment also examines the means of instruction connected to student aptitude and working modes, classroom dynamics as well as teaching methods (Genesee, Hamayan, 1994, Mathews, 1990, in Hamayan, 1995). It should be noted that, for more dependable and optimal results, student assessment should comprise different features such as formative, criterion-referenced, alternative as well as performance evaluation; as a consequence, inferences can be drawn as to whether the overall information provided on learner performance is reliable and the various aspects of group learning such as collaboration, achievement and originality have been thoroughly examined (Boss, Krauss, 2007, in Griva, Kofou, 2017).

6. Conclusion

In brief, classroom observation as a feature of alternative assessment is a non-conventional way of drawing inferences on overall student performance in time. Educators may find that it can be more time-consuming than applying standardised tests as a means of evaluating students; however, learner performance can be evaluated in a more holistic way which considers the students' different talents, tactics and abilities. Unfortunately, traditional testing techniques alone cannot incorporate such characteristics since they fail to assess student aptitude based on the learners' different capabilities when they are exposed to varied learning environments (Graves, Sunstein, 1992, Hamp-Lyons, 1992, in Hamayan, 1995). So, it can be concluded that alternative assessment is a more student-centered approach which prepares individuals for the real world outside the classroom bounds when they will be asked to employ similar skills and strategies that were acquired during the learning process.

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Appendix

Project 1: My own Sport

Topic: Sports

Sessions: 3

Duration of each session: 50 minutes

Aim: Develop creative skills; invent a sport

SKILLS	Speaking: talk about your sport
VOCABULARY	Sports & Equipment
GRAMMAR	Present Simple, Stative verbs
OBJECTIVES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transfer information • Develop thinking skills • Develop creativity • Express Opinion • Make choices • Practise vocabulary on sports/equipment • Practise Present Simple, stative verbs • Design/Draw a poster • Language Across the Curriculum • ICT research skills • 21st century skills • Individual work • Group work • Make a powerpoint presentation • Make an oral presentation
CULTURE	Sports, equipment
MATERIALS	Laptop/PC, IWB, projector, internet access, whiteboard, A3 coloured paper, colouring pens/pencils, scissors, printer, glue
CLASS ARRANGEMENT	Big rectangular table, students sit around it

Project 2: Flying cars

Topic: Flying cars

Sessions: 3

Duration of each session: 50 minutes

Aim: Think of possible problems in the development of flying cars

SKILLS	<p>Writing: write about problems in the development of flying cars</p> <p>Reading: read about problems of flying vehicles</p>
VOCABULARY	Transport verbs
GRAMMAR	Past Simple

OBJECTIVES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transfer information • Read for information • Take notes • Develop thinking skills • Develop creativity • Express Opinion • Make choices • Practise vocabulary on transfer verbs • Practise Past Simple • Language Across the Curriculum • ICT research skills • 21st century skills • Individual work • Group work • Write for the school blog
CULTURE	Travels
MATERIALS	Laptop/PC, IWB, projector, internet access, personal mobile phones/tablets
CLASS ARRANGEMENT	Big rectangular table, students sit around it

Project 3: Healthy pets!

Topic: *Healthy pets*

Sessions: 3

Duration of each session: 50 minutes

Aim: *ICT: Develop research skills; create a poster; give advice on how to keep pets healthy*

SKILLS	Speaking: talk about ways to keep pets healthy
VOCABULARY	Food for pets, pet habits
GRAMMAR	Quantifiers, modals: must/mustn't, should/ought to
OBJECTIVES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transfer information • Develop thinking skills • Develop creativity • Express Opinion • Make choices • Practise vocabulary on pet food, pet habits • Practise quantifiers, modals: must/mustn't/should/ought to • Language Across the Curriculum • 21st century skills • ICT: research skills • Individual work

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Group work • Design/Draw a poster • Make an oral presentation
CULTURE	Pets' Health
MATERIALS	Laptop/PC, IWB, projector, internet access, mobile phones/tablets, whiteboard, A3 coloured paper, colouring pens/pencils, scissors, printer, glue
CLASS ARRANGEMENT	Big rectangular table, students sit around it

PROJECT 1

STUDENT OBSERVATION CHECKLIST

CODE			
Excellent → 5	Very Good → 4	OK → 3	Not Very Good → 2

..... can:

Overall aptitude	
Talk about sports & equipment	
Use vocabulary on sports & equipment	
Use Present Simple	
Use stative verbs	
Invent their own sport	
Make choices	
Express personal opinion	
Make a poster	
Work in a group	
Work individually	
Make a powerpoint presentation	
Make an oral presentation	
ICT skills	
Research online	
Use a pc/laptop/mobile device/tablet	
Use the internet	
21st century skills	
Develop critical thinking	
Develop problem-solving techniques	
Collaborate	

Build team spirit	
Develop digital literacy	
Build creativity	
Feel autonomous	

STUDENT SELF-ASSESSMENT FORM

CODE			
Excellent → 5	Very Good → 4	OK → 3	Not Very Good → 2

Go through your project work and use the code to evaluate yourself.

I can:

Talk about sports & equipment	
Use vocabulary on sports & equipment	
Use Present Simple	
Use stative verbs	
Invent my own sport	
Make choices	
Express my opinion	
Make a poster	
Work with others	
Work alone	
Make a powerpoint presentation	
Speak about my work	
Present my work to others	
Use a laptop/mobile device/tablet	
Use the internet	
Solve problems	
Feel part of a team	
Be creative	
Feel autonomous	

PEER ASSESSMENT FORM: GROUP TO GROUP ASSESSMENT

CODE			
Excellent → 5	Very Good → 4	OK → 3	Not Very Good → 2

Go through your project work and use the code to evaluate the other group.

Group.....can:

Talk about sports & equipment	
Use vocabulary on sports & equipment	
Use Present Simple	
Use stative verbs	
Invent their own sport	
Make choices	
Express their opinion	
Work with others	
Make a powerpoint presentation	
Speak about their work	
Present their work to others	
Use a laptop/mobile device/tablet	
Use the internet	
Solve problems	
Work as a team	
Be creative	
Help others	
Make others understand	

PEER ASSESSMENT FORM: WITHIN GROUP ASSESSMENT

CODE			
Excellent → 5	Very Good → 4	OK → 3	Not Very Good → 2

Go through your project work and use the code to evaluate your group.

My group can:

Talk about sports & equipment	
Use vocabulary on sports & equipment	
Use Present Simple	
Use stative verbs	
Invent our own sport	
Make choices	
Express our opinion	
Work with others	
Make a powerpoint presentation	

Speak about our work	
Present our work to others	
Use a laptop/mobile device/tablet	
Use the internet	
Solve problems	
Work as a team	
Be creative	
Help others	
Make others understand	

PROJECT 2

STUDENT OBSERVATION CHECKLIST

CODE			
Excellent → 5	Very Good → 4	OK → 3	Not Very Good → 2

..... can:

Overall aptitude	
Talk about travel and transportation	
Use vocabulary on travel and transportation	
Use Past Simple	
Transfer information	
Take notes	
Read for information	
Develop thinking skills	
Make choices	
Express personal opinion	
Work in a group	
Work individually	
Write for the school blog	
ICT skills	
Research online	
Use a pc/laptop/mobile device/tablet	
Use the internet	
Digital literacy: write a blog entry	
21st century skills	
Develop critical thinking	

Develop problem-solving techniques	
Collaborate	
Build team spirit	
Develop digital literacy	
Build creativity	
Feel autonomous	

STUDENT SELF-ASSESSMENT FORM

CODE			
Excellent → 5	Very Good → 4	OK → 3	Not Very Good → 2

Go through your project work and use the code to evaluate yourself.

I can:

Talk about travel and transportation	
Use vocabulary on travel and transportation	
Use Past Simple	
Take notes	
Read for information	
Make choices	
Express my opinion	
Work with others	
Work alone	
Write for the school blog	
Speak about my work	
Present my work to others	
Use a laptop/mobile device/tablet	
Use the internet	
Solve problems	
Feel part of a team	
Be creative	
Feel autonomous	

PEER ASSESSMENT FORM: GROUP TO GROUP ASSESSMENT

CODE			
Excellent → 5	Very Good → 4	OK → 3	Not Very Good → 2

Go through your project work and use the code to evaluate the other group.

Group.....can:

Talk about travel and transportation	
Use vocabulary on travel and transportation	
Use Past Simple	
Read for information	
Make choices	
Express their opinion	
Write for the school blog	
Work with others	
Speak about their work	
Present their work to others	
Use a laptop/mobile device/tablet	
Use the internet	
Solve problems	
Work as a team	
Be creative	
Help others	
Make others understand	

PEER ASSESSMENT FORM: WITHIN GROUP ASSESSMENT

CODE			
Excellent → 5	Very Good → 4	OK → 3	Not Very Good → 2

Go through your project work and use the code to evaluate your group.

My group can:

Talk about travel and transportation	
Use vocabulary on travel and transportation	
Use Past Simple	
Read for information	
Make choices	
Express our opinion	
Write a blog entry	
Work with others	
Speak about our work	

Present our work to others	
Use a laptop/mobile device/tablet	
Use the internet	
Solve problems	
Work as a team	
Be creative	
Help others	
Make others understand	

PROJECT 3

STUDENT OBSERVATION CHECKLIST

CODE			
Excellent → 5	Very Good → 4	OK → 3	Not Very Good → 2

..... can:

Overall aptitude	
Talk about ways to keep pets healthy	
Use vocabulary on pet food/pet habits	
Use quantifiers	
Use modals (must/mustn't/should/ought to)	
Make choices	
Express personal opinion	
Make a poster	
Work in a group	
Work individually	
Make an oral presentation	
ICT skills	
Research online	
Use a pc/laptop/mobile device/tablet	
Use the internet	
21st century skills	
Develop critical thinking	
Develop problem-solving techniques	
Collaborate	

Build team spirit	
Develop digital literacy	
Build creativity	
Feel autonomous	

STUDENT SELF-ASSESSMENT FORM

CODE			
Excellent → 5	Very Good → 4	OK → 3	Not Very Good → 2

Go through your project work and use the code to evaluate yourself.

I can:

Talk about ways to keep pets healthy	
Use vocabulary on pet food/pet habits	
Use quantifiers (some, any no, etc.)	
Use modal verbs (must/mustn't/should/ought to)	
Make choices	
Express my opinion	
Make a poster	
Work with others	
Work alone	
Speak about my work	
Present my work to others	
Use a laptop/mobile device/tablet	
Use the internet	
Solve problems	
Feel part of a team	
Be creative	
Feel autonomous	

PEER ASSESSMENT FORM: GROUP TO GROUP ASSESSMENT

CODE			
Excellent → 5	Very Good → 4	OK → 3	Not Very Good → 2

Go through your project work and use the code to evaluate the other group.

Group.....can:

Talk about ways to keep pets healthy	
Use vocabulary on pet food/pet habits	
Use quantifiers (some, any, no, etc.)	
Use modals (must/mustn't/should/ought to)	
Make choices	
Express their opinion	
Make a poster	
Work with others	
Speak about their work	
Present their work to others	
Use a laptop/mobile device/tablet	
Use the internet	
Solve problems	
Work as a team	
Be creative	
Help others	
Make others understand	

PEER ASSESSMENT FORM: WITHIN GROUP ASSESSMENT

CODE			
Excellent → 5	Very Good → 4	OK → 3	Not Very Good → 2

Go through your project work and use the code to evaluate your group.

My group can:

Talk about ways to keep pets healthy	
Use vocabulary on pet food/pet habits	
Use quantifiers (some, any, no, etc.)	
Use modals (must/mustn't/should/ought to)	
Make choices	
Express our opinion	
Make a poster	
Work with others	
Speak about our work	

Present our work to others	
Use a laptop/mobile device/tablet	
Use the internet	
Solve problems	
Work as a team	
Be creative	
Help others	
Make others understand	

COURSEBOOK MATERIAL

Project 1

Project 2

